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THE PSYCHOLOGICAL AND BEHAVIOURAL EFFECTS OF LIMITED-TIME PROMOTIONS ON CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION IN ONLINE SHOPPING: STUDY ON INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN ISTANBUL

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ABSTRACT

This study examines how limited time promotions influence the decision making of consumers on e-commerce platforms. The study examined several variables of limited time promotion, perceived urgency, time pressure, perceived scarcity and purchase intention in order to assess the impact of limited time promotions on consumer behaviour during online shopping process. The study was conducted on international university students studying in Istanbul. For data collection, the questionnaire was used and the total number of respondents was 380. This research fills several gaps in the literature, as many studies on limited time promotions and consumer behaviour are conducted in western contexts, moreover, the moderating role of time pressure is almost underexplored.

Therefore, this research fills these gaps of the current literature. The survey was administered using “Google¹ Forms” and the data was analysed on SPSS statistical package. The results showed that limited time promotions affect consumer purchase intention, moreover, moderating role of time pressure was also found suggesting that the effect of limited time promotions on purchase intention is stronger when consumers are under higher time pressure.

¹ *At the request of Roskomnadzor, we inform you that a foreign person who owns Google information resources is a violator of the legislation of the Russian Federation - ed. note*

In other words, shorter promotion times increase consumers' intention to purchase. In addition, mediating role of both perceived scarcity and urgency were also found and supported, indicating that limited time promotions lead to both perceived urgency and perceived scarcity among consumers that drive consumers to form stronger intentions to purchase the promoted product or service.

Keywords: limited-time promotion, e-commerce, online shopping, perceived urgency, time pressure, perceived scarcity, impulse purchase, purchase intention.

Introduction

Several studies conducted on consumer behaviour in e-commerce found that vast portion of purchases done on online shopping platforms were not based on an actual demand but rather on impulse buying and consumption. Impulse buying is defined as “unplanned immediate purchase driven by emotion” [1]. From the definition given, it becomes apparent that impulse buying is not done based on a logical reason, rather driven by emotions and feeling of the consumer that lead to spontaneous purchase. Interestingly, impulse buying of consumers is usually done for the feeling of short-term happiness and satisfaction [2,3].

For instance, research done by Park et al. [4] showed that impulse buying among consumers is very common. Moreover, another study found that impulse buying can happen several times repeatedly with the same customer and not just once [5], especially, because not all the consumers are logical in their purchases, due to which, spontaneous impulse buying occurs with many of them [6]. Considerable number of studies suggest that impulse buying occurs due to several external and internal stimuli [7], one of such stimuli is marketing activities [8], which limited time offers and promotions are part of [9,10].

Overview

Limited-Time Promotions & Time Pressure. E-commerce businesses frequently use limited-time promotions to attract more customers and drive sales by persuading the customers to rush and purchase the product [11]. Limited-time promotions offer substantial discounts within a limited time for a specific product in order to convince the customer to purchase that product without any hesitation and thinking.

One of the reasons for customers to purchase the products with limited-time promotions is the time pressure, as, time pressure convinces the

customer to buy the product by disrupting customers' established purchase process [12]. As, it was even found that time pressure and time limit push the customer to make purchase decisions quickly in a short amount of time, thus, increasing the purchase intention of customers towards the products having limited-time promotions [13]. Purchase intention is defined as "the customer's attempt and effort to buy the product" [21]. Hence, limited-time promotions aim towards increasing this effort and attempt of customers to buy the specific product.

Moreover, time pressure caused by limited-time promotions results in customers treating time as money and focusing on the opportunity they get from the short time promotion [14]. In addition, another study conducted on this case found that limited-time promotions make the customer refuse to make any other purchase and he or she only purchases the product that is being sold with a limited-time promotion [15].

Not just this, another similar study found that limited-time promotions on products create a sense of rush in consumers as a result of which, customer's purchase intention increases for that specific product, as he or she feels need to purchase the product immediately without losing the opportunity [16].

Perceived Scarcity & Urgency. Perceived scarcity is defined as "individual subjective feelings of scarcity with regard to certain tangible resources or intangible resources" [17]. Urgency on the other hand is defined as "time-based concept that pushes us to act quickly because we worry that we might miss out on something" [18]. Several studies have found that limited-time promotions impose a deadline and insistence on a customer and as a result, customer acts quickly with a fear of missing out and ends up purchasing the product quickly and urgently [19].

Furthermore, another similar research found that limited-time promotions create a sense of scarcity and urgency in consumers, making them feel like they will miss a great deal if they do not act fast and purchase the product [20]. Thereby, this study examines whether time-limited promotions impact the purchase intention of customers with the role of time pressure, perceived scarcity and urgency.

Research Design & Data Collection. This study is a quantitative study with a descriptive research design and utilizes a structured survey for data collection. A total number of 380 valid survey responses were gathered from international university students in Istanbul. The reason for choosing this sample population is due to the fact that Istanbul attracts students from a wide range of countries and cultural backgrounds and doing this research on them will help in examining the cross-cultural consumer behaviour in a real-world setting.

Moreover, snowball sampling method was applied, as it is more cost-effective and less time-consuming compared to other sampling methods.

The data analysis was done on SPSS statistical package. In order to make sure that all the scales are valid and reliable, confirmatory factor analysis and reliability analyses were done after which the scales were found to be highly reliable and valid.

The total number of five scales included were Limited-Time Promotion, Time Pressure, Perceived Urgency, Perceived Scarcity and Purchase Intention.

The main objectives of this study are to investigate the influence of limited time promotions on purchase intention among consumers, to assess the direct effect of limited time promotions on consumers' purchase intention, to examine the mediating role of perceived scarcity and urgency in the relationship between limited time promotions and purchase intention, and to explore the moderating effect of time pressure on the relationship between limited time promotions and purchase intention. Thus, the following hypotheses were formed:

- **H1:** Limited time promotions influence purchase intention among consumers.
- **H2:** Perceived urgency mediates the relationship between limited time promotions and purchase intention.
- **H3:** Perceived scarcity mediates the relationship between limited time promotions and purchase intention.
- **H4:** Time pressure moderates the relationship between limited time promotions and purchase intention.

This study adapted scales from several other studies. A total number of 5 scales with a total number of 20 items were used in this study. All the scales include 5-point Likert scale answer options from “Strongly Agree” to “Strongly Disagree”. Three item “Time Pressure” scale was adapted from Peng et al. (2018) [22]. The scale for measuring propensity towards “Limited-Time Promotion” includes seven items and is adapted from Yilmaz (2019) [23]. Moreover, scale for “Perceived Urgency” is adapted from Gupta (2013) and includes three items [24]. Furthermore, the scale measuring “Perceived Scarcity” was adapted from Gupta and Gentry (2019) and includes two items [25]. Lastly, five item “Purchase Intention” scale was adapted from Amara et al. (2022) [26].

The survey in total includes 30 questions, with the first 10 introductory questions asking the respondent his or her age, gender, place of origin, platforms mostly shopped on, frequency of shopping, types of products shopped for, monthly expenditure on shopping, familiarity with limited-time promotions, frequency of noticing or paying attention to limited-time promotional offers when shopping, and factors important when making a purchase decision.

Moreover, as this study examines four proposed hypotheses, the rejection or support of hypotheses are done based on the data analysis of the responses given by the survey participants. Below is the conceptual framework of the research where each variable and their relationship with one another is indicated:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Hence, the hypotheses and research model suggest that when consumers feel more time pressure such as shorter promotion durations or imminent deadlines, the impact of limited time promotions on their purchase intention is enhanced, thus, indicating the moderating role of the time pressure variable. On the other hand, limited time promotions lead to both perceived urgency and perceived scarcity among consumers that mediate the impact of limited time promotions on consumer purchase intention.

These psychological states then drive consumers to form stronger intentions to purchase the promoted product or service. As a result, limited time promotions indirectly influence purchase intention through the mediating roles of perceived urgency and perceived scarcity. Nevertheless, the direct impact of limited time promotions on purchase intention is also proposed and examined in this study.

Findings & Conclusion

The data analysis showed that LTP has a significant influence on PI, underscoring the effectiveness of LTP in stimulating consumer purchase behaviour, based on which H1 was supported. Moreover, the study also found that PS and PU significantly mediate the relationship between LTP and PI, indicating that limited time promotions lead to both perceived urgency and perceived scarcity among consumers that drive consumers to form stronger intentions to purchase the promoted product or service, hence leading to the support of H2 and H3.

Lastly, TP was identified as a moderator in the relationship between LTP and PI, as higher levels of time pressure intensified the impact of LTP on consumers' PI, therefore, meaning that the effect of limited time promotions on purchase intention is stronger when consumers are under higher time pressure. That being said, higher the time pressure, stronger the impact of limited-time promotion on purchase intention. Thereby, H4 was supported, meaning that all the hypotheses of the study were supported in this study.

In conclusion, this study investigated the influence of Limited Time Promotions (LTP) on consumers' Purchase Intention (PI), with a focus on the mediating roles of Perceived Scarcity (PS) and Perceived Urgency (PU), as well as the moderating effect of Time Pressure (TP). Our findings highlight several key insights into consumer behavior and promotional strategies.

Firstly, due to the significant positive relationship between LTP and PI, the effectiveness of LTP in stimulating purchase intention among consumers is underscored. This findings also aligns with the findings of the study conducted by Yin et al. (2020) [13]. Secondly, mediation analysis revealed that PS and PU mediate the impact of LTP on PI, meaning that LTP leads to a sense of Perceived Urgency (PU) and Perceived Scarcity (PS), which in return enhance the impact of LTP on Purchase Intention (PI). This suggests that consumers' heightened perceptions of urgency and scarcity induced by LTP contribute significantly to their decision-making process when considering purchase decisions, which aligns with the findings of the studies conducted by WebHaptic and WiserNotify [19,20].

Lastly, the study found the moderating effect of TP on the impact of LTP on PI, meaning that when customers experience higher levels of TP, the impact of LTP on PI is increased. Therefore, suggesting that limited-time promotional strategies are effective in prompting immediate purchase decisions under time-limited and pressured conditions. Thus, these findings align with the finding of the study done by Ngolanya et al. (2006) [15].

Thus to summarize, the findings of this study contribute to the understanding of psychological and behavioural impact of limited-time promotions on consumer behaviour. The findings also contribute to the

scientific understanding of consumer behaviour and commits to the scientific knowledge by providing new insights into consumer behavior.

Not just this, our research findings also contribute to the existing literature by enriching the understanding of how LTPs play an important role in consumer behaviour and marketing field, while at the same time offer practical strategies to marketers for effective implementation and management of marketing processes, hence, endue ways to improve marketing effectiveness in competitive markets.

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